

1 Bcl11a during lineage commitment in the human embryo.

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6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of
8 Bcl11a as a lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

9 Citations

10 1. Luc, S., Huang, J., McEldoon, J.L., Somuncular, E., Li, D., Rhodes, C., Mamoor, S., Hou, S., Xu,
11 J. and Orkin, S.H., 2016. Bcl11a deficiency leads to hematopoietic stem cell defects with an aging-like
12 phenotype. Cell reports, 16(12), pp.3181-3194.
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